

1 **Tolerance-associated lymphocyte cell surface markers expressed during transformation and**
2 **senescence bypass.**

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7 We used cellular systems and RNA-sequencing for discovery of malignancy and tolerance-associated cell
8 surface markers induced during transformation. The receptors identified included Ly6K, Ly75 and Ica1L.

9 Citations

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